

DiSSCo Transition Project

**DiSSCo ERIC Socio-economic Impact
Framework (Y1-Y5)**

Work Package 1 - Milestone 1

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Executive Summary

The Distributed System of Scientific Collections (DiSSCo RI) is a pan-European Research Infrastructure aiming at the digital unification of all European natural science collection assets under common curation, policies and practices. The infrastructure will make derived data from approximately 1.5 billion unique biological and geological objects easily Findable, more Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). By uniting over 500 institutions across 23 countries, DiSSCo will provide physical and digital access to collections, expertise and tools for research, education, and innovation.

To maximise its impact, DiSSCo has established four strategic programmes: Digitisation, Access, Innovation, and Training. These programmes aim to transform scientific collections into a globally integrated and accessible research infrastructure, thus enhancing their value for research, economy, society, and policy.

The report outlines a comprehensive socio-economic impact assessment framework for DiSSCo (SEIF), focused on its first five years of operation. The assessment is critical for demonstrating DiSSCo's uniqueness and value in research and society in general. It maps from activities to outputs and outcomes, deriving impact. The framework recognises the non-linear nature of impact pathways, emphasising that various activities can lead to diverse outcomes based on their context and execution.

The methodology employed to measure impact builds upon the work done during the DiSSCo preparatory phase. It is based on an extensive literature review and incorporates best practices from international frameworks (ESFRI, OECD, ALA) and well-consolidated methodologies, specifically RI-PATHS. It utilises key performance indicators (KPIs) that act as proxies for both near and long-term impacts, quantitative metrics that ensure relevance and credibility. The report also uses a recognised standard for indicators and measures developed by the European Commission as part of the Impact Assessment Guidelines, RACER (Relevant, Acceptable, Credible, Easy and Robust).

The impact assessment focuses on four key areas:

1. Science: For instance, impacts on knowledge production, access to information and research practices.
2. Society: For instance, impacts on education, public engagement, policies, regulations compliance and trust in science.
3. Economy: For instance, impacts on job markets, innovation, and corporate efficiency.

4. Policy: For instance, impacts on decision-making processes and governance.

Stakeholders play an integral role in DiSSCo's operation and the assessment framework.

The groups encompass two categories:

1. DiSSCo RI partners: Nodes and strategic partners play a crucial role in the impact assessment of DiSSCo RI.
2. Third parties that benefit from the DiSSCo operation. This category includes funding agencies, other scientific communities than taxonomists, and the public and private sectors.

The SEIF's effectiveness will depend on its implementation, the alignment with stakeholders' expectations, and the regulatory/policy context at a specific time. Guidelines for implementing the impact assessment will be necessary to establish a straightforward process for engaging DiSSCo RI nodes and strategic partners in collecting, analysing and communicating regularly on impact. This process will include monitoring, assessing, and updating the framework when necessary to adapt to rapid changes. The framework does not include guidelines but recommendations for setting up a process conducted in collaboration with DiSSCo RI partners.

In summary, this report aims to present a structured framework for assessing DiSSCo's socio-economic impacts over a critical period for the RI and beyond, offering a pathway to establish long-term benefits across science, society, economy, and policy. This assessment will provide valuable insights for stakeholders and support informed decision-making as DiSSCo progresses toward operational maturity. The framework also includes a preliminary overview of existing tools for collecting information over five years.

Keywords

Socio-economic impact, key performance indicators, impact monitoring, impact assessment, RI-PATH.

List of abbreviations and definitions¹

Core Socio-Economic Impact Indicators (SEII) - a limited group of impact indicators that provide a general picture of the socio-economic impact of a research infrastructure (RI). SEIIs can be used by most RIs, regardless of their structure, role, and scientific domain. They can be integrated into Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to better manage activities and include impact assessment in regular management and decision-making processes.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) - a business's contribution to sustainable development.

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DiSSCo CSO - DiSSCo Coordination and Support Office

EC - European Commission

ELViS - European Loans and Visits System

ERA - European Research Area

ERIC - European Research Infrastructure Consortium

ESFRI - European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures

EU - European Union

FAIR - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability

FDO - FAIR Digital Objects

GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility

IC - DiSSCo Interim Council

IPR - Intellectual property rights

OECD - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

RI - Research Infrastructure

RI-PATH - Methodology to assess RI impact on the economy and contribution to society

SLA - Service level agreement

SME - Small and medium enterprises

WP - Work package

¹ Definitions of SEII, KPI and socio-economic impact follow the OECD in Reference framework for assessing the scientific and socio-economic impact of research infrastructures. Definition of CSR follows the OECD in Corporate Social Responsibility: Partners for Progress, Local Economic and Employment Development (LEED).

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1. Introduction

DiSSCo has established four strategic programmes—Digitisation, Access, Innovation, and Training—to maximise its impact on research, the economy, society, and policy.

According to the European Commission, impact is defined as “all the changes expected to occur due to the implementation and application of a given policy option or intervention, such as investment in a Research Infrastructure and its activities.” These impacts may manifest over different timescales and locations, affect various actors, and be relevant at multiple scales, including local, regional, national, and EU levels. This definition serves as the foundation for DiSSCo's impact framework.

The impact of DiSSCo is anticipated to evolve as the Research Infrastructure matures, transitioning from early development to full operation. A comprehensive overview of DiSSCo's lifecycle, performance, and users' and stakeholders' expectations over time is essential for assessing near- and long-term socio-economic impacts and supporting future decisions on operation.

The focus of the Assessment

The assessment will concentrate on DiSSCo during its first five years, a crucial period for demonstrating its uniqueness and value to research. It will map DiSSCo's activities, outputs, and expected near-term impacts in science. It will serve as an initial step towards establishing long-term socio-economic benefits across scientific, economic, societal, and policy domains. Impact indicators have been identified based on internationally recognised practices, including ESFRI (2019), OECD (2019), RI-PATHS² (Helman et al.,2020), and ALA (Alluvium, 2016).

The framework takes as reference the DiSSCo strategy and the actual knowledge of the community's expectations.

Scope of the Work

This report aims to deliver a comprehensive DiSSCo socio-economic impact indicators framework (SEIF) that encompasses:

- An overview of DiSSCo's impact areas, strategic goals and stakeholders.
- Key impact indicators for the first five years of DiSSCo ERIC operation.

2. DiSSCo Impact Areas

² RI-PATHS Toolkit Glossary, <https://ri-paths-tool.eu/en/glossary>

This report builds upon the work done during the preparatory phase and consolidates the impact areas identified³ into four impact areas as follows:

1. **Science:** Impacts on knowledge production, access to information, scientific attractiveness, research practices, infrastructure, common policies and standards, innovation and research collaboration.
2. **Society:** Impacts on capacity building and education, societal challenges, communication and outreach, addressing public and private challenges, trust in science, faster excellent research outputs availability, benefits to the ERA, use of open FAIR data, efficiency, best use of resources, social inclusion, corporate social responsibility, carbon footprint or engagement between society and science.
3. **Economy:** Impacts on costs associated with information access and use, curation and availability of knowledge, curricula development, addressing public and private challenges, job markets and economic growth, innovation, alignment with national priorities and long-term sustainability, collaboration with the private sector, corporate efficiency or uptake of accessible data sets.
4. **Policy:** Impacts on decision-making processes, uptake of information for policies, regulations compliance, new regulations, policies and implementation measures, better governance, advice to public and private sectors, or change in the fundamentals of research practices.

3. Stakeholders

DiSSCo strategic programmes respond to a wide range of users' priorities and needs identified during the preparatory phase⁴. Based on that, together with the interest of DiSSCo to establish long-term collaborations with target stakeholders, particularly in the science-policy realm and with strategic partners, the framework delineates categories of stakeholders (see Table 1)⁵. The groups include two categories:

1. **DiSSCo RI partners:** Nodes and strategic partners who play a crucial role in the impact assessment of DiSSCo RI.
2. **Third parties that benefit from the DiSSCo operation.** This category includes funding agencies, scientific communities, and the public and private sectors.

³ During the preparatory phase, the following areas of impact were identified: job creation and economic growth; scientific advancements; industry and Innovation; education and public engagement; infrastructure and long-term sustainability; and policy and governance.

⁴ DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable D1.1 Report on Life sciences use cases and user stories & DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable D1.2 Report on Earth sciences use cases and user stories. It also includes results from continuous dialogue with national nodes and potential service providers.

⁵ DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable D1.4 Report on socioeconomic impact indicators of DiSSCo and DiSSCo-enabled research and research applications.

A common element keeps both categories interlinked: All have defined interests that align with DiSSCo's mission and contribute to its long-term sustainability. In general terms, DiSSCo stakeholders can be broadly defined as individuals and/or entities who interact with and/or benefit, directly or indirectly, from DiSSCo's outputs.

Stakeholder	Interests
Funders and Science-policy bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Help to achieve the vision and mission of the communities they represent/are interested in ● Return of investment ● Strategic planning ● Optimise investments and resource planning ● Define support programmes & strategies at the regional and EU level
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improve capacity to develop research activities ● Open and FAIRification of collections
Data managers, data curators, stewards & data, informatics professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhance the discoverability of data and increase collaboration ● Enhance the effectiveness, recognition and impact of data curators ● Improve data and the reusability of data ● Contribution to open science ● Support compliance with national policies and help secure funding ● Support efficiency and stronger engagement with users
DiSSCo communities of practices (collection curators, taxonomists)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Harmonisation of practices through common curation, standards and policies ● Annotation and curation through MAS ● Capacity building ● Increase efficiency and lower costs ● Increase visibility of collections and experts ● Open data and FAIRification of collections
Private sector & public sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Develop innovation products ● Use of digital resources ● Support decision-making process ● Strengthen the market job
Strategic Partners (i.e. EU RIs, IO, EU bodies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Leverage technological developments ● Promote interoperability and integration at the scientific domain or regional level ● Support the European Research Area ● Support the implementation of Directives and other regulations
DiSSCo RI Facilities & National Nodes	<p>Improve and upgrade the services provision Better coordination with the ERIC</p>

	<p>Improve dialogue with national funders Reach wider communities</p>
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Table 1. Shortlist and interests of stakeholders in DiSSCo.

Each stakeholder group has specific expectations from DiSSCo, but at the same time, DiSSCo actively aligns its activities with their priorities to ensure mutual benefit and long-term collaboration. The following sections outline how that influences the research infrastructure's development.

Funding Agencies: DiSSCo aligns with national roadmaps and European regulations to meet the needs of EU and national agencies. The RI aims to support informed decision-making processes through data and standard community practices, ensuring maximum return on investment across long-term digitisation, access, training programs, and innovation.

Science-Policy Advisory Bodies: DiSSCo plays a pivotal role in shaping effective, evidence-based policies by leveraging data quality, data access, capacity building, and innovation. Collaboration will expand the potential impact of the RI in the design and implementation of policies, regulations, and funding frameworks.

Scientific Communities include communities of practices linked to biological and geological diversity and communities across research domains (i.e. health, ecology, climate, genomics, chemicals).

Data managers, curators, stewards, and data and informatics professionals are crucial in ensuring data quality, interoperability, and accessibility. They expect DiSSCo to enhance data discoverability, reusability, and collaboration through standardised formats, FAIR principles, and shared infrastructures. DiSSCo aligns with these needs by providing harmonised data policies, interoperable digital frameworks, and tools that improve data management efficiency and FAIRness.

Industry includes users (who derive value from DiSSCo services for the delivery of their commercial activity), suppliers of DiSSCo RI services (procurement), and partners in common projects.

Strategic Partners⁶ is any entity that wishes to significantly contribute to the DiSSCo vision on a long-term basis. These partners expect DiSSCo to provide a robust,

⁶ Art.18 of the DiSSCo Statutes version approved on Sept 23rd, 2024 by the DiSSCo Interim Council

interoperable framework that facilitates cross-disciplinary collaboration and data integration. In turn, DiSSCo aligns with these expectations by promoting interoperability, developing shared policies, and fostering technological advancements that support seamless collaboration across research domains. By engaging with strategic partners, DiSSCo strengthens its position within the European Research Area and contributes to the broader goal of open science.

National Nodes include a well-organised and committed community of collections-holding institutions organised at a national level that enhances the effectiveness and sustainability of DiSSCo. In return, DiSSCo will, through service provision and programmes, unleash the potential of the collections.

4. Methodology - How we measure the impact

The methodology is based on a sound understanding of (i) DiSSCo's mission and strategic goals, (ii) DiSSCo's programs and (iii) community expectations. The framework uses KPIs as proxies for near- and long-term impact.

The framework is informed by an exhaustive literature review and analysis conducted during DiSSCo's preparatory phase. It incorporates international best practices (e.g., OECD, ESFRI, GBIF assessment, ERIC Forum, RI-PATH) and the European Commission's Impact Assessment Guidelines. Additionally, the framework aligns with the European Commission's Impact Assessment Guidelines, utilising the RACER criteria (Relevant, Acceptable, Credible, Easy and Robust) as a recognised standard for indicators and measures.

While preparing the framework, the team opted to use the RI-PATH⁷ methodology to design the socio-economic impact framework for DiSSCo. The decision was made for several reasons: (i) it addresses the particular characteristics of Open Science RIs, (ii) it allows the tool to be tailor-made, and (iii) the tools are straightforward and can be well communicated and assessed.

The primary objective of the assessment is to achieve long-term benefits. While these long-term impacts are often challenging to estimate or plan, they provide a clear direction for the RI's intended impact. Defining and steering activities to create the desired impact would be straightforward if the RI could control every aspect of the process. However,

⁷ <https://ri-pat/en/impact-pathwayshs-tool.eu>

achieving results is complex, and many factors influencing outcomes may be beyond its control. According to the RI-PATH, the RI manages activities and directs the outputs generated from those activities, which fall within its "Sphere of Control."

In contrast, outcomes are typically outside this sphere. In some instances, the perceived impact depends on how users or stakeholders interpret the results. Here, the RI can still exert influence, as it maintains direct relationships with the target audience within its "Sphere of Influence." Nonetheless, the socio-economic or political context often shapes long-term impacts, leading to varying interpretations. Effective communication by DiSSCo with stakeholders and the broader public is crucial in mitigating the risk of being overlooked as a key driver of socio-economic benefits.

DiSSCo's framework adapts the RI-PATH methodology to identify four key impact areas: society, science, policy, and economy. It also defines five target stakeholder groups: science-policy bodies and funders, research communities, strategic partners, private sector (industry), and DiSSCo national nodes.

Regarding metrics, the framework includes performance indicators, each serving as a relevant proxy for impact. The implementation of this framework must recognise that while performance indicators demonstrate DiSSCo's operational effectiveness and goal attainment, socio-economic indicators assess how that performance benefits the economy and society at a specific point in time. These metrics will be closely monitored to ensure their effectiveness in providing valuable data over time, ultimately guiding DiSSCo towards achieving a sustainable and positive impact on society and the economy.

As a regional digitisation centre, I want to offer the highest possible quality and extent of specimens' digitalisation so that more natural history excellence data is available for research and innovation (A need) > mass digitisation programme (DiSSCo programme/activity) > Increases accessibility and usability of data for scientific knowledge production (output) > Improve quality and number of publications in relevant journals and research projects (impact in science) > First and second level citations in publications with high-impact factor (Indicator).

Impact pathways

RI-PATHS establishes pathways for assessing potential impact and defining impact assessment, as simplified causal chains of events that connect activities carried out by the RI to identifiable effects on the economy and broader society." The pathways describe

non-linear narratives from activity to output to outcome and expected impact, and end with metrics (indicators) for the assessment (see Fig. 1).

Fig.1 shows a non-linear pathway from activity to impact. The solid line represents near impact. The dotted line represents the long-term impact.

The same activities can lead to different results that also differ in terms of proximity to the cause of impact. In that sense, outcomes can be near and/or long-term benefits.

The baseline data is set at zero as outcomes from DiSSCo RI are not operational and activities have yet to be measured. By following this structural approach, DiSSCo aims to create a meaningful process for evaluating its contribution to societal global challenges. The framework will need to be assessed regularly during operation to guarantee that it becomes a driving force for excellence in performance, optimisation of resource use, engagement with users and stakeholders, and successful fulfilment of DiSSCo's mission and strategic goals.

4.1. Principles & standards

Those are the principles that inspired the preparation of the framework:

1. No one fits all - DiSSCo develops its impact framework based on common best practices and tools, but focuses on DiSSCo-specificities and uniqueness.
2. Flexibility and regular updates - The framework is meant to be reviewed regularly.
3. Innovate to empower - DiSSCo strives to understand user communities and focus on service and solution development according to their needs. DiSSCo will design and provide fit-for-purpose, sustainable, and robust solutions together with and for user communities.
4. Transparency & Trust - The work aims to develop clear guidance for the implementation and assessment of the future socio-economic impact of DiSSCo. The work seeks transparency and will keep regular communication with stakeholders about using existing and well-consolidated tools and practices.

- Inclusiveness - The work aims to engage with the DiSSCo community of partners for the review and final preparation of the framework and its implementation guidelines.

The study uses the RACER standard:

- Relevant, as it should measure the right thing
- Accepted by target users/stakeholders
- Credible for non-experts
- Easy to monitor
- Robust against manipulation

5. DiSSCo ERIC Strategic Goals and Activities

DiSSCo describes its ambition in terms of benefiting society and research in general in its Strategy⁸ as follows:

DiSSCo vision: Knowledge and evidence about nature's diversity are available to all.

DiSSCo mission: Unleash the full potential of natural history collections by bringing them together in a distributed, interoperable European research infrastructure, making them physically and digitally open, accessible, and usable for all forms of research and innovation.

Strategic goals & activities

DiSSCo focuses on maximising the impact of its collective assets (in both data and expertise) and sharing the benefits of the knowledge with the broadest possible audience. The ultimate reason is to contribute meaningfully to responses addressing biodiversity loss and climate change. DiSSCo has defined four main business programmes with specific overarching goals, objectives and an open list of activities, as follows:

Digitisation Programme

What is the issue	How DiSSCo responds
Digitisation investments are scattered and not coordinated	A pan-European digitisation programme that ensures optimum, scientifically-driven prioritisation of content mobilisation across all European assets.

Table 2. Issue/Response within DiSSCo Strategic Digitisation Programme

⁸ DiSSCo Prepare Milestone 7.1 DiSSCo Strategy & operational planning.

1. Programme Goal: Accelerate and lower barriers to digitisation across European natural science collections.
2. Strategic Objectives
 - a. Develop strategies for prioritising digitisation: Create a framework for prioritising digitisation efforts at various levels, grounded in community consensus, to ensure relevance and effectiveness.
 - b. Develop open digitisation workflows: Establish open workflows, comprehensive training programs, and best digitalisation practices to standardise processes and enhance accessibility across the community.
 - c. Establish and operate regional digitisation centres & centres of excellence: Create dedicated facilities that serve as hubs for digitisation, offering expertise, resources, and support to enhance overall capacity and collaboration in the field.
3. Digitisation Programme Implementation: DiSSCo will collaborate with multiple partners to effectively implement the digitisation programme, focusing on the following key components:
 - a. Prioritisation strategy for digitisation: Develop and implement a strategy that identifies which collections should be digitised, prioritising scientific, cultural, and societal relevance.
 - b. Regional digitisation centres & centres of excellence: Establish a network of regional centres that provide targeted support and resources for digitisation efforts alongside centres of excellence that focus on advanced methodologies and innovation in digitisation practices.
 - c. Funding prospection for digitisation: Actively seek and secure funding opportunities to support digitisation initiatives, ensuring sustainable financial backing for ongoing projects.
 - d. Specialisation plan: Create a plan to define areas of specialisation, allowing facilities or nodes to develop expertise in specific collections or digitisation techniques.
 - e. Collections digitisation dashboard: Develop a digital dashboard that provides real-time tracking and reporting on the progress of digitisation efforts, making data accessible to stakeholders and the public.

- f. Budget for the first phase of operations & funding prospection: Establish a detailed budget for the initial phase of operations and strategies for ongoing funding efforts to support the programme.

Integrated Access Programme (Digital and Physical access)

What is the issue	How DiSSCo responds
Physical and virtual access are disconnected	An orchestrated multi-modal access programme for European collections.
Collections development is fragmented, and investment decisions are taken based only on institutional or national gaps	Services that allow a birds-eye-view of the taxonomic and geographic gaps in biodiversity and geodiversity surveying, as well as related European-wide policies that would enable a pan-European orchestrated collections development programme.

Table 3. Issue/Response within the DiSSCo Strategic Access Programme

1. Programme Goal: Create and implement multimodal, standardised, and innovative routes for accessing and curating collections' information, including transnational, remote, and digital access.
2. Strategic Objectives
 - a. Develop and facilitate a pan-European transnational and remote access programme: Establish a cohesive framework that promotes seamless access to collections across Europe, enabling researchers and the public to engage with diverse collections remotely.
 - b. Deliver robust online capabilities for access and scientific curation of specimens' information: Champion the concept of collections' twinning, which involves generating and maintaining digital twins of physical specimens. This will enhance the scientific curation process and provide detailed online information for users.
 - c. Widen the reach of collections-derived information: Expand access to collection-derived information for a broader audience, including industry stakeholders and cultural heritage communities. It will foster collaboration and innovation, driving new applications of collections data.
 - d. Budget for the first phase of operations & funding prospection: Establish a detailed budget for the initial phase of operations and strategies for ongoing funding efforts to support the programme.

3. **Integrated Access Programme Implementation:** DiSSCo will collaborate with multiple partners to effectively implement the integrated access programme, which will focus on the following key components:
- a. **The ELViS portal:** Develop and operate the ELViS (European Loans and Visits System) portal as a central point for accessing and curating collections information, facilitating user-friendly navigation and interaction with specimens' digital representations.
 - b. **Transnational and virtual access:** Transnational and Virtual Access Programme: Implement a comprehensive programme that supports the practical application of transnational and virtual access, providing resources and support for users to engage with collections effectively. Establish a clear policy that outlines the principles and guidelines governing transnational and virtual access to collections, ensuring equitable and responsible use of resources.
 - c. **Collections digitisation dashboard:** Use the dashboard to track progress and enhance the overall management of collections information.
 - d. **Regular communication with users:** Establish ongoing communication channels to keep users informed about developments, gather feedback, and update them on progress, ensuring that the programme remains responsive and user-centred.

Data & Applications Programme (Services)

What is the issue	How DiSSCo responds
Taxonomic expertise across our local collections is declining	A community curation model that can pull expert resources across locations, transforming institutionally restricted curation to a shared community model.
Trust in mobilised digital records is declining because of quality concerns	Re-unification of all data classes derived from the study of collection objects provides unified access to the digital twins of physical specimens and extended provenance information.
Data derived from the study of voucher specimens is disconnected	A new concept of the digital extended specimen is at the core of DiSSCo's data architecture. The digital specimen is an informationally enhanced digital twin of a physical specimen. A digital specimen acts as a human-readable and machine-actionable knowledge unit that

	integrates all data from the study of the physical object.
The use of collections in scientific outputs is poorly monitored	Deploying a unified persistent identification system for digital specimens would further facilitate tracking individual specimens across scientific outputs.

Table 4. Issue/Response within the DiSSCo Strategic Data & Applications Programme

1. Programme Goal: Develop and maintain the required data infrastructure and offer a portfolio of e-services that add value to the core data infrastructure of DiSSCo, providing easy-to-access solutions to identified end users.
2. Strategic Objectives:
 - a. Develop and maintain the digital extended specimens (DES) infrastructure: Create an infrastructure that enables the management of extended specimens as machine- and human-readable, actionable knowledge units. This allows for better integration and use of data across systems.
 - b. Implement novel community curation services: Establish community curation services that leverage expertise from a diverse pool of scientists while integrating data from a wide range of external scientific sources. This collaborative approach will enhance the quality and breadth of the available information.
 - c. Deploy hybrid intelligence approaches: Hybrid intelligence methodologies to enhance knowledge production by combining machine learning technologies with human insights. This strategy aims to increase the volume and quality of data linked to specimens and derived from them.
3. Data and Applications Programme Implementation: DiSSCo will establish and operate in collaboration with various service providers to implement the Data and Applications Programme, focusing on the following key components:
 - a. E-services for FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs): Develop e-services such as DiSSCover and implement a specialisation plan to support the effective use of FAIR Digital Objects within the ecosystem.
 - b. DiSSCo architecture based on FDOs: Design and maintain an architecture compatible with FAIR principles and actively promote and facilitate the mobilisation of FDOs to ensure widespread access and usability.

- c. Digital specimen repository: Establish a digital repository for specimens, allowing for secure storage, easy access, and efficient management of digital specimens.
- d. Data policy: Develop a data policy that outlines the governance, usage, and sharing principles for data within the DiSSCo RI.
- e. Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) Policy: Implement a clear IPRs policy to protect the rights of data creators while facilitating users' access to data.
- f. Data community standards: Establish community standards for data management and sharing to ensure consistency and quality across the DiSSCo network and international initiatives.
- g. Research data management plan: Create a research data management plan that outlines best practices for data handling, storage, and sharing among users and partners.
- h. Strategic partnerships for co-creation and provision of services: Form strategic partnerships with relevant stakeholders to co-create services that meet user needs and enhance overall functionality.
- i. Service Level Agreements (SLAs): Develop SLAs to regulate service provision at the DiSSCo RI level, ensuring accountability and quality of service.
- j. International cooperation on standards and FDOs: Engage in international collaborations to align on standards and best practices, facilitating global interoperability.
- k. Budget for the first phase of operations & funding prospectation: Establish a detailed budget for the initial phase of operations and strategies for ongoing funding efforts to support the programme.

Capacity Building programme

What is the issue	How DiSSCo responds
Taxonomic expertise across our local collections is declining	A community curation model that can pull expert resources across locations, transforming institutionally restricted curation to a shared community model.

Table 5. Issue/Response within the DiSSCo Strategic Training Programme

1. Programme Goal: Ensure partners and users confidently supply and utilise data through DiSSCo and its e-services.
2. Strategic Objectives:

- a. Provide self-assessment tools for digital maturity: Equip DiSSCo facilities with tools to assess their level of digital maturity. That includes offering guidelines to improve compliance with DiSSCo's technical and policy framework.
 - b. Organise and facilitate training: Develop and implement training programs within the DiSSCo consortium to build in-house capacity. These initiatives aim to enhance digital skills and competencies within the European collections community.
 - c. Lead in international standards development: Take a leadership role in the international community by refining and implementing standards that ensure DiSSCo's data and e-services adhere to FAIR principles. This will also impact research, policy, and innovations across the scientific, private, and societal sectors.
 - d. Budget for the first phase of operations & funding prospectation: Establish a detailed budget for the initial phase of operations and strategies for ongoing funding efforts to support the programme.
3. Training Programme Implementation: DiSSCo will collaborate with multiple partners to effectively implement the training programme, focusing on the following key components:
- a. Training for Trainers programme: Develop a comprehensive "Training for Trainers" programme that empowers individuals within institutions to train others, thus amplifying the reach and effectiveness of digital skills training.
 - b. Citizen Science programme: Establish a Citizen Science programme that engages the public in data collection and curation activities, fostering a sense of community involvement and enhancing the breadth of data available for research.
 - c. Budget for the first phase of operations & funding prospectation: Establish a detailed budget for the initial phase of operations and strategies for ongoing funding efforts to support the programme.
 - d. Communication, outreach, and engagement strategy: Implement a communication, outreach, and engagement plan to raise awareness about training opportunities, encourage participation, and foster collaboration among stakeholders, partners, and the wider community.

6. DiSSCo SEII Matrix⁹

The table below maps activities across DiSSCo's strategic programmes and identifies outputs, short-term impact, and indicators to evaluate socio-economic impact over the first five years of operation. Furthermore, the most likely primary and secondary stakeholder groups are indicated.

The table here includes relevant SEIIs, focusing on those able to provide more accurate data with existing tools and minimal resource use.

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https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1RCFMNCISfE_pCEze4nYDfHclECunSKPBfOmvRvjAPTg/edit?usp=sharing

Four programmes towards socio-economic impact by DiSSCo RI				Impact Areas		
STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES	OUTPUT	DESCRIPTION	SCIENTIFIC	IMPLEMENTATION	
DIGITISATION						
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing strategies for prioritising digitisation at various levels based on community consensus; - Develop open digitisation workflows, training, and best practices; - Establish & operate regional digitisation centres & centres of excellence. 	Digitisation programme with prioritisation of activities based on user needs and digitisation on demand.	Increases accessibility and usability of data for scientific knowledge production	Improve the quality and number of publications in relevant journals and research projects	1. Number of collections digitised and new topics after 5 years	DiSSCo Collections Dashboard & DiSSCo Helpdesk	
		A new pool of data-driven innovation based on new topics for research	Users advocate for specific national funding programmes based on available data and new publications	2. Scientific collaborations with other RIs (joint projects)	DiSSCo repository - projects/proposals portfolio	
		Digitisation on demand.				
	Specialisation plan	Development of regional digitisation centres & centres of excellence.	Well-informed decisions on the allocation of resources and procurement	Improve collections network; improve training, education, and outreach	3. Number of programs on digitisation on demand	DiSSCo Collections Dashboard & DiSSCo Helpdesk
			Alignment with national priorities and national funding programmes	Improve DiSSCo's economy of scale; facilitate discussions with stakeholders on investment		
	Collections Digitisation Dashboard	Increase understanding of data and experts across the EU;	Improve VA/TA access to data and experts; reduce costs on loans and visits		4. Satisfaction of people trained	Survey
			Improve access to training		Satisfaction of people trained	Survey

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES	OUTPUT	DESCRIPTION	SCIENTIFIC	IMPLEMENTATION	ECONOMY	IMPLEMENTATION
INTEGRATED ACCESS							
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and facilitate a pan-European transnational and remote access programme; - Deliver robust and comprehensive online capabilities for the access and scientific curation of specimens' information by championing the concept and process of collections' twinning (the generation and maintenance of specimens' digital twins); - Widen the reach of collections-derived information to more users and communities (e.g. industry, cultural heritage). 	ELVIS portal;	Seamless access to virtual and physical collections for a wider array of users	Unique access point for integrated data analysis and interpretation; reduce costs from loans and visits: reduce carbon footprint	5. Number of users 6. Users satisfaction	ELVIS & Surveys	9. Average of hours of DiSSCo data usage per research project	Survey
	Transnational and virtual access programme	Efficient and lower-cost access to data	improves management, reduces time to access, reduces costs with VA, increases social responsibility	7. Number of TA/VA	ELVIS	10. Estimation of time saved by researchers	Survey
		Increase knowledge production		8. First and second-level citations for publications	Text mining		
	Access Policy						

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES	OUTPUT	DESCRIPTION	SCIENTIFIC	IMPLEMENTATION	ECONOMY	IMPLEMENTATION	SOCIETY	IMPLEMENTATION
DATA AND APPLICATIONS									
- Develop and maintain the digital extended specimens infrastructure	Data infrastructure and core services	Available integrated, curated data to allow knowledge access,	Citation and recognition are two of DiSSCo's added values. Also, support transdisciplinary	8. First and second-level citations for publications	Text mining	14. Scientific collaborations with other RIs (joint projects)	DiSSCo repository - projects/proposals portfolio		

<p>as machine- and human-readable and actionable knowledge units;</p> <p>-Implement novel community curation services that muster expertise from a vast pool of scientists and data from the broadest possible external scientific sources;</p> <p>- Deploy hybrid intelligence approaches to knowledge production by coupling machine</p>		citation and recognition	y research; level up the capacity of small/medium collections						
	Data policy	Community endorsement of standards and policies		11. Number of collections aligned with DiSSCo policy	Specialisation plan				
	IPRs policy	Community endorsement of standards and policies							
	Research data management plan	Data integration and access are the main resources given by the RI	Increase common management and efficiency, lower costs for collections						
	Strategic partnership for co-creation and provision of services	Joint development of new services and/or training at a lower cost:		2. Scientific collaborations with other RIs (joint projects)	DiSSCo repository - projects/proposals portfolio				
	International cooperation on standards and FDOs	Community endorsement of standards and policies		12. Presence of DiSSCo in relevant standardisation committees	DiSSCo repository - participation in international bodies/national networks				

learning technologies and human contributions to increase the volume and quality of specimen-linked and specimen-derived data.	FAIR integrated data creation	Reduce costs; open access to FAIR data						
	DiSSCover service	Provision of annotated and curated data, taxonomic expertise identification; DES increases data quality & completion	Citation and recognition are added values of DiSSCo.	13. Research results fed into shared data sets/repositories	Text mining			15. Use of open data (access and download)

STRATEGIC OBJECTIVES	ACTIVITIES	OUTPUT	DESCRIPTION	SCIENTIFIC	IMPLEMENTATION
CAPACITY BUILDING					
-Provide tools to DiSSCo facilities to self-assess the level of digital maturity and provide roadmaps to improve facilities' compliance with DiSSCo's technical and policy framework; -Organise and facilitate training within the DiSSCo consortium to build in-house capacity and enhance the European collections' community digital skills and competencies; -Lead within the	Training for Trainers programme;	DiSSCo training program	Training program with special attention to gender and geographical inclusion	16. Student satisfaction	Survey
		Short missions as part of collaboration with strategic partners		17. Number of SM	Survey across facilities
	Citizen Science programme;	Citizen Science programme;			
	Communication, Outreach and engagement plan;	Website, events, workshops, training programme, Raising awareness			
	DES creation	New experiences for visitors to the museums	Exhibitions and educational tools based on DiSSCo DES architecture can lead to new experiences with		

international community in refining and implementing standards to ensure that DiSSCo's data and e-Services are FAIR and impact research, policy and scientific/private sector/societal innovations.			users, better engagement and education programmes.		
	Training (CEST platform)				

OTHER	ACTIVITIES	OUTPUT	DESCRIPTION	POLICY	IMPLEMENTATION
OTHER ACTIVITIES					
International relations & provision of advice	Participation in national/regional committees	Improve well-informed decisions of national authorities		18. Participation of RI in local and regional networks	DiSSCo repository - participation in international bodies/national networks

Table 6. DiSSCo SEII Matrix

7. Recommendations for implementation

To enhance third-party impact monitoring, the leading party (a responsible person appointed at the DiSSCo ERIC Central Hub) must establish a steady stream of valuable impact-relevant information from the DiSSCo ERIC internal business owners, the nodes.

A comprehensive route for implementing the impact assessment framework is necessary, starting with:

1. Node engagement: establish a process for engaging nodes to ensure seamless and long-term implementation;
2. Metrics: secure endorsement by the community of indicators and methodology, and update them when necessary;
3. Data collection: identify methodologies to collect data (DiSSCo services, surveys, text mining, repositories) that align as much as possible with existing mechanisms at the node;
4. Ownership: define ownership within the DiSSCo organisation for data gathering, analysis and reporting on indicators among the DiSSCo ERIC and nodes;
5. Baseline assessment: conduct a state-of-the-art assessment prior to implementation to facilitate assessment against reference data;
6. Data management plan: develop a plan that covers the data lifecycle, from collection to archiving. New developments may require automated processes;
7. Data Analysis and Reporting: design and implementation of the information management system for data gathering, analysis and reporting;
8. Capacity Building: guaranteeing the distributed team has enough understanding to collect and assess correctly and adapt to changes.

DiSSCo must keep nodes engaged through the lifecycle of the five-year assessment process. The objectives are (i) to collect reference data for regular impact assessment and (ii) to manage stakeholders' expectations. The framework distinguishes between primary and secondary stakeholders based on the immediacy of the impact. Frequently, nodes will also be primary stakeholders. For instance, training directly impacts DiSSCo communities and staff from facilities, making them primary stakeholders, while in a long-term perspective, training will also increase capacity building and improve the job market at the national level, which might impact academia (secondary stakeholders).

Until DiSSCo becomes an ERIC, DiSSCo nodes and funding agencies at the Interim Council (DiSSCo IC) will be key actors in discussing processes and metrics and testing them. This is

expected to continue after the DiSSCo Transition project, and feedback will be received from the national nodes and the Interim Council, the decision-making body for legal and financial matters. As soon as the impact assessment is approved, it will be necessary to move towards implementation.

8. Conclusions

The DiSSCo Socio-Economic Impact Framework (SEIF) is a practical tool for demonstrating and continuously improving DiSSCo's socio-economic value. It is designed to be adaptable and evolve alongside DiSSCo's maturity.

To ensure its effectiveness, two fundamental elements must be established early in the process:

1. **Clear Processes:** Define processes for data management (collection, analysis, reporting, and storage).
2. **Dedicated Team:** Maintain a team responsible for overseeing these processes, ensuring continuity and stakeholder engagement. This team should be skilled in interpreting information accurately and effectively communicating value to various stakeholders.

To ensure the sustainability of the assessment process, the team has identified indicators that aim to minimise the use of resources (human, budget and time) by leveraging existing services and the expected contributions of personnel working partially or fully for DiSSCo ERIC. Mastering the demonstration of impact across various dimensions will require time and may evolve based on shifting priorities and socio-economic conditions. However, this adaptability is crucial for the long-term sustainability of the RI, its future development, and the trust DiSSCo builds among partners and stakeholders.

Regular assessment of five-year impact will be instrumental in successfully planning and executing across DiSSCo domains, e.g., service provision, resource investment, training needs, or the prioritisation of strategic partnerships.

By focusing on the following key areas, DiSSCo will be well-positioned to achieve meaningful socio-economic impacts that contribute to research, innovation, and societal benefits:

1. **Digitisation & FAIR Data:** DiSSCo is actively developing new technologies to enhance the digitisation and FAIRification of collections, ensuring that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The large-scale

digitisation efforts, supported by the DiSSCo digitisation programme, will dramatically increase access to and usage of Open and FAIR-integrated data from these collections. This initiative improves not only the efficiency of data utilisation but also prioritises key research needs, thereby enhancing digitisation workflows and better aligning them with national research roadmaps.

2. **Seamless Transnational & Virtual Access:** The European Loans and Visits System (ELViS service) is a central access point that streamlines data analysis and enhances overall efficiency in utilising collections while reducing costs. This initiative also underscores DiSSCo's commitment to social responsibility by making valuable data more accessible across borders.
3. **Research & Innovation Impact:** Knowledge production based on DiSSCo's extended specimens will significantly influence research and innovation in various ways. The impacts include new research niches, increased available literature, and influence national research priorities. Enhanced data quality will also encourage collaboration with partners from various fields, including the private sector (for innovation) and science-policy bodies (for assessment, monitoring, or informed decision-making). The socio-economic impact of investment in innovation is expected to be substantial once the Research Infrastructure reaches operational maturity.
4. **Standardisation & Collaboration:** Implementing common management practices, policies, and standards will facilitate data sharing, interdisciplinary research, and funding opportunities across various sectors.
5. **Data Enrichment & Recognition:** DiSSCo is developing services that enable experts to enrich and extend data associated with specimens using machine and human agents. This integrated and curated data will facilitate provenance, citation, and recognition, directly influencing practice communities across different domains.
6. **Training & Capacity Building:** DiSSCo's training program aims to support professionals, citizen scientists, and new learners while ensuring inclusivity. The "Training for Trainers" initiative will empower institutions to maximise the benefits of the RI, supported by self-assessment tools that promote policy harmonisation and cost-effective public investment.
7. **Strategic Partnerships:** Fostering strategic partnerships with the public and private sectors will further enhance DiSSCo's capabilities and outreach.

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